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D^0 meson Reconstruction and Expected Statistical Precision on Nuclear Modification Factor (R_{eAu})

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Abstract

In this note, we present the results on the secondary vertex resolution of D^0 mesons with the ePIC detector, reconstructed from the $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ decay channel, in the central, forward, and backward rapidities. I also describe the analysis strategy for the reconstruction of D^0 with machine learning (ML) method and the extraction of projected statistical uncertainty on the nuclear modification factor R_{eAu} .

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1 Introduction

In electron–proton ($e+p$) collisions, heavy quarks (charm and beauty), due to their large masses, are predominantly produced at the early stage of the interaction via the photon–gluon fusion (PGF) process, as shown in the Fig. 1. There are mainly two kinematic regimes based on the momentum transfer (Q^2), known as photoproduction, which corresponds to $Q^2 < 1 \text{ GeV}^2$, while deep-inelastic scattering (DIS) for $Q^2 > 1 \text{ GeV}^2$ [3]. The PGF is a leading order (LO) process in which a virtual photon (for DIS event) from the electron interacts with the gluon from the proton and produces a heavy-quark pair. Further contributions to heavy-flavor production originate from resolved-photon (γ) processes, where the photon is treated as a hadronic object [4]. The produced heavy quarks hadronize into color neutral hadrons such as D^0 , D^+ , and Λ_c .

Figure 1: A Feynman diagram illustrating the Photon-Gluon Fusion (PGF) process for the production of a charm-quark pair in $e+p$ collisions.

Because of their large masses ($> \Lambda_{QCD}$) and production mechanism (PGF), the measurements of heavy-flavor production in $e+p$ collisions will allow us to access a wide range of physics studies at the EIC, such as, such as testing and constraining Monte Carlo (MC) models based on perturbative Quantum Chromodynamics (pQCD) calculations, constraining the gluon parton distribution function (PDF) at moderate to high- x , studying the transition of heavy quarks into hadrons (hadronization), and investigating the role of intrinsic charm (IC) in the proton [5], etc.

Similar measurements can also be performed in $e+A$ collisions to investigate the effect of nuclear environment on their production and transport properties as shown in the Fig. 2. For example, previous measurements of charged hadron multiplicities in semi-inclusive DIS (SIDIS) off nuclei by the HERMES collaboration have shown a clear suppression compared to those off the deuteron target [6]. However, the underlying physics mechanism causing such a suppression is still under discussion, with two primary candidates: parton energy loss before hadronization vs. hadron absorption after hadronization in cold nuclear matter (CNM), as both of them can describe the HERMES measurements.

Figure 2: A schematic illustration of a parton traversing through cold nuclear matter, with hadron formation occurring outside the nucleus (left) and inside the nucleus (right) [1].

At the EIC, charm quarks will be copiously produced over a wide pseudorapidity (η) regime, making it possible to measure D^0 mesons with very high precision [5]. We can measure CNM effect as a function of x_B , z (hadron energy fraction), and p_T of the D^0 meson, given by the expression below.

$$x_B = \frac{Q^2}{2p_{\text{proton}} \cdot q}, \quad z = \frac{p_{\text{proton}} \cdot p_D}{p_{\text{proton}} \cdot q}, \quad (1)$$

Here, x_B is the Bjorken scaling variable, $Q^2 = -q^2$ is the negative four-momentum transfer squared of the exchanged virtual photon, p_{proton} is the four-momentum of the incoming proton, p_D is the four-momentum of the reconstructed D^0 meson, and q is the four-momentum of the virtual photon. In the proton rest frame, the variable z represents the fraction of the virtual photon's energy carried by the D^0 meson in the proton's rest frame. Thanks to its large mass, the parton energy loss picture will lead to a suppression of D^0 mesons at high z and an enhancement at low z in $e+A$ collisions with respect to that in $e+p$ collisions, while the hadron absorption scenario should result in a suppression at all z [6, 7]. These two distinct behaviours make D^0 meson measurements at the EIC a powerful tool for identifying the underlying mechanism and studying properties of cold QCD matter.

In this analysis note, the analysis strategy for the reconstruction of the D^0 meson is demonstrated, which is used to extract the distance of closest approach (DCA) distribution for primary and secondary tracks, secondary vertex resolution, invariant mass spectra without and with machine-learning (ML)-based selection, and the expected projected statistical uncertainty of the nuclear modification factor R_{eAu} . Finally, a conservative estimation of systematic uncertainties is performed based on existing experiments as well as full simulations of the ePIC tracker to extract the final results.

2 Analysis details

The analysis procedure starts with the reconstruction of DIS events using the full simulation of the ePIC tracker. This section will describe a detailed procedure used for the reconstruction of the D^0 meson, DCA distribution, secondary vertex resolution, invariant mass plots with ML, and the statistical projection of the nuclear modification factor of the D^0 meson.

2.1 D^0 meson Reconstruction

For the reconstruction of the D^0 meson and its charge conjugate, the combinatorial pairing is performed using oppositely charged reconstructed tracks within an event. To further reduce the number of combinations, the particle identification criterion is applied, incorporating realistic PID performance from the parameterized lookup tables. The use of particle identification also allows the evaluation of the invariant mass of the pair, as given by the equation below.

$$m_{D^0} = \sqrt{(E_K + E_\pi)^2 - (\tilde{p}_K + \tilde{p}_\pi)^2} \quad (2)$$

The invariant mass of track pairs originating from the decay of a true D^0 meson contributes to the signal peak region of the invariant-mass spectrum, while combinatorial background from misidentified track pairs populate a broad mass range, contributing both under the signal peak as well as in the sideband (tail) regions of the distribution. To achieve a good signal-to-background ratio, additional selection cuts on various topological variables are applied, which effectively reduce the combinatorial background.

2.1.1 Topological Variables

For each event, the primary vertex position is determined using the CentralTrackVertices algorithm, which uses information from reconstructed tracks, such as track parameters and their corresponding covariance matrices. In this case, the vertex resolution depends on the multiplicity of the events which usually improves with the number of tracks ($\sim \sigma_{DCA}/\sqrt{N_{tracks}}$). Once primary vertex is reconstructed, a track can be propagated to the point of closest approach to that vertex position. It allows to estimate the distance of closed approach (DCA) for a particle with respect to the primary vertex position as shown in Fig. 3 based on helix swimming method from the STAR experiment [2].

To access more topological variables, the reconstruction of the decay vertex, also known as the secondary vertex (SV) for the pair, is necessary. The SV position can be determined using the helix swimming method as well as a χ^2 minimization approach.

Figure 3: A schematic illustrating the D^0 decay ($\rightarrow K^- \pi^+$) along with various topological variables [2].

- SV with Helix Swimming Method:** The method assumes each track to be a helix in a uniform magnetic field, and the coordinates of the distance of closest approach (dca) between two helices are denoted as $d\vec{ca}_1$ and $d\vec{ca}_2$. From these, the decay vertex position (\vec{SV}) and the distance of closest approach between the two tracks (DCA_{12}), and the spread around the vertex position (σ_{vtx}) can be evaluated using Eq. 3.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \vec{SV} &= \frac{1}{2} \left(d\vec{ca}_1 + d\vec{ca}_2 \right), \\
 DCA_{12} &= \left| d\vec{ca}_1 - d\vec{ca}_2 \right|, \\
 \sigma_{vtx} &= \sqrt{|d\vec{ca}_1 - \vec{SV}|^2 + |d\vec{ca}_2 - \vec{SV}|^2}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

In this case, the uncertainties on the x and y components of the vertex position are given by the expressions below.

$$\sigma_{SV_{x,y}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sigma_{dca_{1x,y}}^2 + \sigma_{dca_{2x,y}}^2 + 2 \text{cov}(dca_{1x,y}, dca_{2x,y})}{4}} \tag{4}$$

In the simplest case, assuming the uncertainties as uncorrelated and similar for the two tracks, Eq. 4 indicates that the uncertainty is approximately given by $\sim \sigma_{dca}/\sqrt{2}$, as expected for two tracks. In general, the secondary vertex resolution ($\sim \sigma_{dca}/\sqrt{N_{\text{daughters}}}$) is poorer than the primary vertex resolution ($\sim \sigma_{dca}/\sqrt{N_{\text{tracks}}}$) due to the smaller number of contributors. This also indicates that the separation between the primary and secondary vertices is driven by the secondary vertex resolution. Additional topological variables, including the decay length (dl), the cosine of the pointing angle ($\cos \theta$), the distance of closest approach of the D^0 meson (DCA_{D^0}), and the significance of DCA_{xy} ($DCA_{xy}/\sigma_{DCA_{xy}}$), can be derived using the reconstructed track information and the

primary and secondary vertices.

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{d}l &= S\vec{V} - P\vec{V}, & \cos\theta &= \frac{\vec{d}l \cdot \vec{p}_{D^0}}{|\vec{d}l| |\vec{p}_{D^0}|}, \\ \cos\theta_{xy} &= \frac{\vec{d}l_{xy} \cdot \vec{p}_{D^0,xy}}{|\vec{d}l_{xy}| |\vec{p}_{D^0,xy}|}, & \text{DCA}_{D^0} &= |\vec{d}l| \sin\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

- **SV with a χ^2 Minimization Method:** In this approach, the track parameters and the corresponding covariance matrices are used to determine the secondary vertex position. Once a track is reconstructed, the track parameters ($l_0, l_1, \phi, \theta, q/p, t$) and their covariances (error matrix) are estimated at the point of closest approach to the origin of the laboratory frame. The track parameters at the DCA position in the global coordinate system (\vec{r}, \vec{p}, q) can then be estimated using the relations given below.

$$\begin{aligned} x &= -l_0 \sin\phi, & y &= l_0 \cos\phi, & z &= l_1, & \text{charge} &= \text{sign}\left(\frac{q}{p}\right) \\ p_x &= p \cos\phi \sin\theta, & p_y &= p \sin\phi \sin\theta, & p_z &= p \cos\theta. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The χ^2 minimization method assumes five parameters, of which three correspond to the decay vertex position (v_x, v_y, v_z), and the remaining two are the path lengths (s_1, s_2) along the two helices as shown in Fig. 4. Finally, the expression given in Eq. 7 is minimized using TMinuit in the ROOT framework [8] to estimate the secondary vertex position and the corresponding covariances.

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(x_1 - v_x)^2}{\sigma_{x_1}^2} + \frac{(x_2 - v_x)^2}{\sigma_{x_2}^2} + \frac{(y_1 - v_y)^2}{\sigma_{y_1}^2} + \frac{(y_2 - v_y)^2}{\sigma_{y_2}^2} + \frac{(z_1 - v_z)^2}{\sigma_{z_1}^2} + \frac{(z_2 - v_z)^2}{\sigma_{z_2}^2}. \quad (7)$$

Here, $\vec{r}_{s_1} = (x_1, y_1, z_1)$ and $\vec{r}_{s_2} = (x_2, y_2, z_2)$ denote the positions at the parameterized path lengths s_1 and s_2 along the two helices. The corresponding uncertainties appearing in the denominator are taken from the track covariance matrices and also transformed into the global coordinate system. This method is used to estimate the secondary vertex position and can be easily extended to decays with three or more daughter tracks. After estimating the secondary vertex position using this approach, all the topological variables can be evaluated using the expression in Eq. 3 and 5.

2.2 Secondary Vertex Resolution

At the MC generation level, prompt D^0 mesons are produced at the collision vertex and subsequently decay into daughter particles at a distance of $c\tau \sim 123 \mu\text{m}$, with the daughters having a common origin at the decay vertex (SV_{mc}). At the reconstructed level, they are smeared with respect to their common origin due to detector effects, such as finite spatial resolution and multiple scattering as shown in Fig. 5. Once the tracks are reconstructed, the

Figure 4: A schematic illustrating the D^0 decay ($K^-\pi^+$), along with the track parameters at the DCA as well as at a given path length (s) position.

decay vertex for the pair (SV_{rec}) is determined using the χ^2 minimization approach, and the residuals for each coordinate are evaluated with respect to the true decay vertex position. The resulting distributions are fitted with a double-Gaussian function, and the root mean square (RMS) of the distribution is considered as the secondary vertex resolution.

Figure 5: A schematic representation of D^0 decay vertex at the truth (left) and reconstructed (right) level.

2.3 Invariant Mass Reconstruction

To obtain the invariant mass spectra in $e + p$ collisions, the D^0 reconstruction code was executed on the produced October simulation campaign files for the D^0 sample as well as for the neutral current (NC) DIS samples. Particle identification was applied within the code, while the topological selection based on the ML approach was applied at a later stage. The ML training was performed independently in different y bins, using true signal pairs from the D^0 sample and background pairs from the DIS sample. At backward rapidity, the training is performed over the full combined p_T range for the statistical projection of R_{eAu} due to limited statistics for $p_T < 1$ GeV/ c , while for the invariant-mass analysis in subsection 3.3 and 3.4, it is carried out for $p_T > 1$ GeV. In contrast, at mid- and forward rapidity, the training is always performed separately in two intervals: $p_T < 1$ and $p_T > 1$ GeV. For the final invariant

mass spectra, the signal pairs are taken from the D^0 sample, while the background pair are obtained from the DIS sample, applying the appropriate scaling factor between the two. A similar procedure was also repeated for $e + \text{Au}$ collisions to extract the invariant mass spectra using particle identification only and ML-based topological selections.

2.4 Estimation of Projected Statistical Uncertainty on $R_{e\text{Au}}$

The nuclear modification factor ($R_{e\text{Au}}$) for the D^0 meson is defined as the ratio of the signal yields in $e + \text{Au}$ collisions to those in $e + p$ collisions. To estimate the statistical uncertainty, the invariant mass spectra are first obtained with a loose topological selection (known as preselection) and then fitted with a Student's t function combined with a linear function. After this, the significance is estimated using the signal (S) and background (B) candidates with the expression given in Eq. 8. This represents the significance with loose topological selection. Therefore, for the estimation of significance with ML, boosted decision tree (BDT) efficiencies for signal (ϵ_{sig}) and background (ϵ_{bkg}) are applied to signal and background to obtain the significance with ML as given by the expression below.

$$\text{Significance} = \sqrt{\frac{S}{S+B}}, \quad \text{Significance (ML)} = \sqrt{\frac{S \cdot \epsilon_{sig}}{S \cdot \epsilon_{sig} + B \cdot \epsilon_{bkg}}}. \quad (8)$$

The inverse of the significance is known as the relative statistical uncertainty ($\sigma(S)/S$) on the signal measurement. Similarly, the relative statistical uncertainty is also estimated for $e + \text{Au}$ collisions with ML approach. Finally, the statistical uncertainty on $R_{e\text{Au}}$ in a given y and p_T bin is estimated using the Eq. 9 below.

$$\frac{\sigma(R_{e\text{Au}})}{R_{e\text{Au}}} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma(S)}{S}\right)_{e+p}^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma(S)}{S}\right)_{e+Au}^2}. \quad (9)$$

2.5 Data and Monte Carlo Samples

The results presented in this analysis note are obtained by analyzing $e+p$ and $e+\text{Au}$ collisions at $\sqrt{s} = 63 \text{ TeV}$ (10×100 with $Q^2 > 1 \text{ GeV}^2$). The simulation is based on the PYTHIA event generator [9] for $e+p$ collisions, while $e+\text{Au}$ collisions are simulated with the Benchmark eA Generator for LEptoproduction (BEAGLE) [10]. There are mainly two kinds of samples for each system known as D^0 sample and neutral current DIS sample. D^0 enriched sample is prepared filtering DIS events in such a way that each event consist at least a $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$. The simulated samples used in the analysis is from the October 2025 campaign as proposed by the collaboration. The samples corresponding to different collision systems are located at the following paths.

D^0 Sample _{$e+p$} = /volatile/eic/EPIC/RECO/25.10.3/epic_craterlake/SIDIS/D0_ABCONV/
pythia8.306-1.1/10x100/q2_1/hiDiv/

DIS Sample_{e+p} = /volatile/eic/EPIC/RECO/25.10.0/epic_craterlake/DIS/NC/10x100/
minQ2_1/

D⁰ Sample_{e+Au} = /volatile/eic/EPIC/RECO/25.10.3/epic_craterlake_without_zdc/
SIDIS/D0_ABCONV/HFsim-BeAGLE/BeAGLE1.03.01-2.0/
eAu/10x100/q2_1to10000/

DIS Sample_{e+Au} = /volatile/eic/EPIC/RECO/25.10.2/epic_craterlake_without_zdc/
DIS/BeAGLE1.03.02-1.0/eAu/10x100/q2_1to10/

The D⁰ sample from e+p collisions was used to estimate the secondary-vertex resolution in different rapidity (y) and transverse-momentum (p_T) bins. For the training of the machine-learning (ML) model based on a boosted decision tree (BDT), the signal D⁰ pairs were taken from the D⁰ sample, while the background pairs were obtained from the DIS sample corresponding to each collision system. Depending on the available statistics, the model was trained either separately in individual y and p_T bins or using combined bins. Finally the results for R_{eAu} were extracted in different y and p_T bins using ML, which demonstrates the capabilities of EIC to access the physics over a wide kinematic regimes.

3 Results and Discussions

In this section, the results will be presented with detailed procedure for each analysis that is expected to be approved during the upcoming physics forum.

3.1 Transverse DCA distributions

This section (by Rongrong Ma, BNL, USA) describes the procedure to produce the figure where the transverse DCA distributions for primary and secondary π^\pm are compared.

Input dataset:

- /volatile/eic/EPIC/RECO/25.10.3/epic_craterlake/SIDIS/D0_ABCONV/
pythia8.306-1.1/10x100/q2_1/hiDiv/

Source code:

- https://github.com/eic/preTDR_JetsHF/tree/main/Heavy-flavor/DCA_PrimVsSec

Analysis procedure:

- MC primary vertex is used for calculating track DCA in the transverse plane ($x - y$)
- Primary π^\pm and secondary π^\pm from D^0 decay are selected based on MC information
- Comparison is done in different π^\pm η and p_T bins, as shown in Fig. 6

Figure 6: Distance of closest approach in the transverse plane (DCA_{xy}) with respect to the MC primary vertex for π produced at the collision vertex (dashed) as well as those from D^0 decays (solid). The panels from left to right correspond to four different π pseudorapidity bins within $-2.0 < \eta < 3.0$, while the top and bottom rows show two different p_T intervals ($0.5 < p_T < 1.0$ and $1.0 < p_T < 1.5$ GeV/c), respectively.

3.2 Secondary Vertex Resolution

The secondary vertex resolution is estimated in x and y direction using the D^0 sample from $e+p$ collisions in different four rapidities (y) and two p_T bins as shown in Fig. 7. The resolutions in the x and y directions are similar, as expected from the symmetric layout of the detector setup in $r\phi$ plane. The corresponding distributions are fitted with a double-Gaussian function, and the RMS of the fitted distribution is quoted as the secondary-vertex resolution, as defined in Eq. 10. The resolution improves at high p_T , with the best resolution achieved at mid-rapidity in the range $2 < p_T < 5$ GeV/c of about $31 \mu\text{m}$.

$$f(x) = A_{\text{core}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma_{\text{core}}^2}\right) + A_{\text{tail}} \exp\left(-\frac{(x - \mu)^2}{2\sigma_{\text{tail}}^2}\right), \quad (10)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{eff}} = \sqrt{\frac{A_{\text{core}}}{A_{\text{core}} + A_{\text{tail}}} \sigma_{\text{core}}^2 + \frac{A_{\text{tail}}}{A_{\text{core}} + A_{\text{tail}}} \sigma_{\text{tail}}^2}.$$

Since the χ^2 fitting algorithm is implemented within the ROOT framework using the `TMinuit`

Figure 7: Secondary vertex resolution for the x and y coordinates in four rapidity bins ($-2.0 < y < 3.5$) and two p_T bins ($0 < p_T < 1$ and $2 < p_T < 5$ GeV/c). The distribution in the x direction is fitted with a double Gaussian function and the RMS is quoted as the vertex resolution in each panel [\[link to the code\]](#).

minimizer, the pull distributions are also examined in different y and p_T bins. The distributions are centered around zero, and their widths (standard deviations) are found to be less than 1.5, as shown in Fig. 8, indicating a proper estimation of the uncertainties.

3.3 Invariant Mass of D^0 meson in e+p Collisions

For this study, the code was executed on D^0 and DIS samples in (e+p) collisions with $Q^2 > 1$ GeV². The event statistics for the two samples at different steps of the selection are shown in Fig. 9. From the DIS sample, the branching ratio for ($D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$) can be verified by taking the ratio of the corresponding entries, $4096/106805 \sim 3.84\%$. The D^0 sample is created filtering ~ 1747 M PYTHIA8 DIS events with the cross section $\sigma = 4.63 \times 10^5$ pb such

Figure 8: Pull distributions of Secondary vertex resolution for the x coordinate in four rapidity bins ($-2.0 < y < 3.5$) and three p_T bins ($0 < p_T < 1$, $1 < p_T < 2$, and $2 < p_T < 5$ GeV/ c).

that each event consist at least a D^0 meson, while for DIS sample $\sim 5M$ events are simulated as shown in the left and right panel of Fig. 9. Therefore, the simulated D^0 sample correspond to the integrated luminosity ($L_{\text{int}} = 1747M / (4.63 \times 10^8 \text{fb})$) of 3.7fb^{-1} .

The phase space of reconstructed true signal and background pairs in the D^0 sample is also shown in Fig. 10, which indicates that the statistics for the reconstructed D^0 mesons are larger at forward y than at backward. This behavior is mainly driven by the fact that most D^0 mesons are produced at backward rapidity (low x_B) via PGF process and are subsequently boosted toward forward rapidity due to the momentum of the target (proton) as shown in Fig. 11. In the next step, the signal from the D^0 sample, with only particle-identification (PID) selections applied, is projected into four (y) bins for $p_T > 1$ GeV/ c (black markers) and fitted with a Student's (t) function (red line). Subsequently, resampling is performed for an integrated luminosity of 10fb^{-1} ($\sim 4721M$ events), shown by the green markers; see Fig. 12. Similarly, the resampling to (10fb^{-1}) is also performed for the background pairs using a linear fit function for the DIS sample in the same y bins, as shown in Fig. 13. Later, the signal pairs are merged with background pairs in each y and p_T range, the resulting distribution correspond to (10fb^{-1}) is give in Fig. 14 using only particle identification to reject the combinatorial background.

A machine-learning model, based on a Boosted Decision Tree (BDT) binary classifier, was developed using the `hipe4ml` library [11]. The classifier was trained after a loose preselection ($1.6 < m_{D^0} < 2.5$ && $d_{0,xy}^\pi < 10 \text{mm}$ && $d_{0,xy}^K < 10 \text{mm}$ && decay length $< 100 \text{mm}$) using

Figure 9: Event statistics for e+p collisions, the D^0 sample (Left) and NC DIS sample (Right) showing statistics at different steps of the selection.

Figure 10: Phase space true signal pairs (Left) and background pair (Right) in D^0 sample.

Figure 11: Bjorken x_B vs y and momentum (p) of D^0 meson at the generation level in D^0 sample that clearly demonstrate that D^0 at low x_B are boosted at forward y .

Figure 13: Projection of reconstructed invariant mass of background pairs ($e+p$) in four y bins and $p_T > 1$ GeV/c in DIS sample (black marker). The distribution is fitted with a linear function and resample to integrated luminosity of 10fb^{-1} .

Figure 14: D^0 invariant mass spectra (e+p) using only particle identification in four y bins and $p_T > 1 \text{ GeV}/c$ in DIS sample (black marker). The distribution is fitted with a Student's (blue) and a linear function (green).

topological features of true signal pairs from the D^0 sample, while the background pairs were taken from the DIS sample. The signal and background statistics used for the training are summarized in Table. 1. The model was trained in four different (y) bins for $p_T > 1$ GeV/c, and the corresponding BDT efficiencies were estimated for each case; see Fig 15. In the bin, $-2 < y < -1$, a fluctuation is observed due to the lower statistics available in the training, which can be improved in the future. In this case, a BDT threshold of 0.60 is chosen for all the y bins to demonstrate the qualitative effect on the signal and background using topological cuts based on the ML approach. If a BDT threshold of 0.6 is applied, the remaining signal will be the signal with only PID selection multiplied by the BDT efficiency (ϵ_{signal}). Similarly, the remaining background will be multiplied by the corresponding BDT efficiency ($\epsilon_{\text{background}}$). In this case the function shapes for signal and background are assumed same after ML. The plots demonstrate the effect of applying ML-based topological selections, which significantly suppress the background, as shown in Fig. 16.

Table 1: Statistics used in ML (1–10 GeV/c) for e+p collisions.

p_T (GeV/c)	> 1
$-2 < y < -1$	Sig: 4555, Bkg: 4555
$-1 < y < 1$	Sig: 22039, Bkg: 22039
$1 < y < 2$	Sig: 21334, Bkg: 21334
$2 < y < 3$	Sig: 8852, Bkg: 8852

3.4 Invariant Mass of D^0 meson in e+Au Collisions

The e+Au collisions are simulated using the BeAGLE (Benchmark eA Generator for LEp-toproduction) framework. A similar procedure was performed for e+Au collisions using the corresponding D^0 and DIS samples. The event summary plots for the two samples are shown in Fig. 17. Here D^0 sample is created filtering $\sim 300.3\text{M}$ NC DIS events with a cross section of $0.3413 \mu\text{b}$, correspond to the integrated luminosity L_{int} of 0.88 fb^{-1} . The simulated DIS sample consists $\sim 5\text{M}$ DIS events, the branching ratio for $D^0 \rightarrow K^- \pi^+$ is about $\sim 3.65\%$.

The sampling of the D^0 invariant-mass distribution from the D^0 sample and the background from the DIS sample is performed in each y and p_T range for an integrated luminosity of 10 fb^{-1} (3413 M events) as shown in Fig. 18 and 19. The invariant mass spectra with merged signal and background fitted with a student and a linear function in different y and p_T bins can also be found in Fig. 20.

In the next step, similar to the e+p collisions, the ML model (statistics in Table. 2) is trained after the loose preselection ($1.6 < m_{D^0} < 2.5$ && $d_{0,xy}^\pi < 10 \text{ mm}$ && $d_{0,xy}^K < 10 \text{ mm}$ && decay length $< 100 \text{ mm}$) in each rapidity range and $p_T > 1$ GeV/c, and the BDT efficiencies for signal and background D^0 mesons are extracted as shown in Fig. 21. Finally, the invariant mass spectra are extracted in each y and p_T bins with only PID information

Figure 15: BDT efficiencies from ML training for signal and background D^0 meson in four y bins and $p_T > 1$ GeV/ c in $e+p$ collisions.

Figure 16: Invariant mass plots for the D^0 meson with only PID selection (black markers) and with topological selection including PID based on the ML approach (red markers) are shown in four (y) bins for $p_T > 1$ GeV/c. The plots are normalized to the entries corresponding to 10 fb^{-1} and show that, using the ML approach, the background can be suppressed by a factor of ~ 10 [link to the code].

Figure 17: Event statistics for e+Au collisions, the D^0 sample (Left) and NC DIS sample (Right) showing statistics at different steps of the selection.

Figure 18: Projection of reconstructed invariant mass of signal pairs (e+Au) in four y bins and $p_T > 1$ GeV/c in D^0 sample (black marker). The distribution is fitted with a Student's (t) function and resampled to integrated luminosity of 10fb^{-1} .

Figure 19: Projection of reconstructed invariant mass of background pairs ($e+Au$) in four y bins and $p_T > 1$ GeV/c in DIS sample (black marker). The distribution is fitted with a linear function and resample to integrated luminosity of 10fb^{-1} .

Figure 20: D^0 invariant mass spectra (e+Au) using only particle identification in four y bins and $p_T > 1 \text{ GeV}/c$ in DIS sample (black marker). The distribution is fitted with a Student's (blue) and a linear function (green).

as well as the topological selection based on the ML approach, which again show that the background can be significantly suppressed as shown in Fig. 22.

Table 2: Statistics used in ML (1–10 GeV/c) for e+Au collisions.

p_T (GeV/c)	> 1
$-2 < y < -1$	Sig: 8126, Bkg: 8126
$-1 < y < 1$	Sig: 41348, Bkg: 41348
$1 < y < 2$	Sig: 34763, Bkg: 34763
$2 < y < 3$	Sig: 13629, Bkg: 13629

3.5 Projected Statistical Uncertainty on R_{eAu}

To estimate the projected statistical uncertainty on R_{eAu} in different rapidity ranges ($-2 < y < -1$, $-1 < y < 1$, and $1 < y < 3$) and p_T bins ($0 < p_T < 1$, $1 < p_T < 2$, $2 < p_T < 5$, and $5 < p_T < 10$ GeV/c), a sampling procedure similar to that described in the previous section is adopted. In the case of the eAu sample, the number of background pairs is too low in the highest p_T bin ($5 < p_T < 10$ GeV/c) to perform a linear fit, as shown in Fig. 23. For this reason, the distribution of background pairs are compared between the ep and eAu samples in different rapidity and p_T bins, as shown in Fig. 24. The comparison indicates that the background shape is similar within uncertainties, due to the use of the same particle identification and preselection cuts ($1.6 < m_{D^0} < 2.5$ && $d_{0,xy}^\pi < 100$ mm && $d_{0,xy}^K < 100$ mm && decay length < 100 mm). ‘

Therefore, to address this, the background pairs normalized by the p_T bin (dN/dp_T) are fitted with a Lévy–Tsallis function as shown in Fig. 25 and subsequently interpolated into this bin ($5 < p_T < 10$ GeV/c). The shape of the background function is taken from the ep sample as the shape is similar for the other p_T bins.

Due to limited simulated statistics (as given in Table. 3 and 4), the training for ML in the backward rapidity region is performed in a single combined p_T bin, while at mid and forward rapidities it is performed in two bins ($0 < p_T < 1$, $p_T > 1$ GeV/c). The projected statistical uncertainty of the nuclear modification factor is estimated using the procedure described in subsection 2.4 as shown in Fig. 26. The results show the better statistical precision at mid and forward rapidity relative to backward rapidity due to the lower statistics of D^0 mesons.

Figure 21: BDT efficiencies from ML training for signal and background D^0 meson in four y bins and $p_T > 1$ GeV/ c in $e+Au$ collisions.

Figure 22: Invariant mass plots for the D^0 meson with only PID selection (black markers) and with topological selection including PID based on the ML approach (red markers) are shown in four (y) bins for $p_T > 1$ GeV/c. The plots are normalized to the entries corresponding to 10 fb^{-1} and show that, using the ML approach, the background can be suppressed by a factor of ~ 10 [link to the code].

Figure 23: Comparison of background pairs for D^0 meson at mid (left) and forward (right) rapidities and p_T bin of $5 < p_T < 10$ GeV/c, showing the too small statistics in the case of eAu sample.

Figure 24: Comparison of background pairs for D^0 meson in three rapidity ranges (top, middle, bottom rows) and three p_T bins; ($0 < p_T < 1$, $1 < p_T < 2$, and $2 < p_T < 5$ GeV/c).

Figure 25: Background pairs were fitted with the Lévy–Tsallis function to estimate the yield in the highest (p_T) bin ($5 < p_T < 10$ GeV/(c)) at mid-rapidity (left) and forward rapidity (right).

Figure 26: Relative statistical uncertainty on the nuclear modification factor the backward, mid, and forward rapidity ranges in different p_T bins. The statistical precision is better at mid and forward rapidities relative to the backward [link to the code].

Table 3: Available statistics for ML e+p after preselection for R_{eAu} statistical projection.

p_T (GeV/c)	0–1	> 1
$-2 < y < -1$	Sig: 7913, Bkg: 7913	
$-1 < y < 1$	Sig: 35137, Bkg: 35137	Sig: 22205, Bkg: 22205
$1 < y < 3$	Sig: 52583, Bkg: 52583	Sig: 30430, Bkg: 30430

Table 4: Available statistics for ML e+Au after preselection for R_{eAu} statistical projection.

p_T (GeV/c)	0–1	> 1
$-2 < y < -1$	Sig: 16903, Bkg: 16903	
$-1 < y < 1$	Sig: 82115, Bkg: 82115	Sig: 41596, Bkg: 41596
$1 < y < 3$	Sig: 99094, Bkg: 99094	Sig: 48686, Bkg: 48686

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